

Statistical analysis plan: Emulation of a Target Trial in a DEVOTE inspired population using the Danish registries

The purpose of DEVOTE was to evaluate the safety of insulin Degludec in patients with type 2 diabetes. This double blinded randomized control trial included 7637 patients to receive either insulin glargine (n=3819) or insulin degludec (n=3818) once daily prior to bedtime. This trial evaluated first occurrence events of major cardiovascular events (death from cardiovascular disease (CVD), non-fatal stroke and non-fatal myocardial infarction (MI)) as a primary composite outcome. Additionally, severe hypoglycemia was analyzed as a secondary outcome. A total of 6509 (85.2%) of patients had established CVD or/and chronic kidney disease at baseline and the mean age was 65 years. Mean Hba1c levels were 8.5+-1.7%. Primary outcome occurred in 325 (8.5%) patients in the degludec group and 356 (9.3%) patients in the glargine group (HR: 0.91, CI: 0.78-1.06) (for non-inferiority, P<0.001). At 24 months mean Hba1c was 7.5+-1.2% in each group whereas fasting plasma was significantly lower in the degludec group. Hypoglycemia occurred in 187 (4.9%) in the degludec group and 252 (6.6%) in the glargine group, yielding an absolute difference of 1.7% (HR 0.6 P<0.001 for superiority). In conclusion, degludec was non-inferior with regards to CVD death in high risk patients compared to glargine and had superior effects with regards to reducing risk of hypoglycemia.

Link to trial: <https://www.nejm.org/doi/full/10.1056/NEJMoa1615692>

Research questions

The question of interest in this study is to compare insulin degludec to insulin glargine on cardiovascular disease (CVD) outcomes in a population resembling the trial patients in DEVOTE, as specified under the study population. We want to compare the risk of CVD outcomes at 1-5 years of follow-up, employing different treatment regimes.

Observed data

In this section, the available data is presented on a level of granularity that would enable other researchers to reproduce the data management necessary for carrying out this project.

Study population

The in- and exclusion criteria for the trial and the emulation depend on the date on which they are evaluated. The recruitment process for the two study forms is different. In the real trial, the criteria are likely only evaluated once per patient, but the same patient may be evaluated multiple times. For the emulated trial, we can scan the registers and basically evaluate the criteria on a day-to-day basis. For the emulated trial we define time zero as the first date the patient redeems one of the pharmacotherapies of interest and fulfills the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Centrally, several therapies include more than one of the active substances of interest, we are, however, only included in monotherapies, defined by ATC codes in Table 3.

Inclusion criteria

Trial	Emulation	
Men or women with type 2 diabetes	Patients with type 1 diagnosis are excluded	
HbA1c levels of over 7%	HbA1c over 53 mmol/mol at the latest measurement before baseline, max 1 year before. This excludes all those without an HbA1c measurement.	
Age \geq 50 years at screening	Age \geq 50 years at the treatment of interest initiation	
-	Patients who immigrated into the country less than 10 years prior to baseline are excluded.	

<p>High risk CVD patient: defined as having at least one of the following prior to inclusion: myocardial infarction, stroke, revascularization, documented cardiac stenosis, stress test or ischemic heart disease, chronic heart failure NYHA II-III or chronic renal disease 30-60 eGFR</p>	<p>Prevalent disease defined by any occurrence, looking 20 years back from baseline. eGFR defined based on lab results looking 2 years back from baseline.</p> <p>Diagnosis codes present in table 2. (1,3,4,5,10,11,12)</p>	
<p>or if above is not fulfilled: Age over 60 AND micro or macro albuminuria or hypertension and verified left ventricular hypertrophy or ABI < 0.9 or left ventricular systolic/diastolic dysfunction by imaging.</p>	<p>Albuminuria is defined based on laboratory results within 1 year from baseline. Defined as having a urine albumine creatinin ratio of above 30 mg/g Hypertension defined based on medication use.</p>	

Exclusion criteria

Trial	Emulation
<p>An acute coronary or cerebrovascular event in the previous 60 days</p>	<p>Evaluated as having had a myocardial infarction or stroke within the last 60 days from baseline.</p>
<p>Planned revascularization of coronary, carotid or peripheral arteries.</p>	<p>Not applicable</p>
<p>The estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) was less than 30 or being on renal dialysis of any type</p>	<p>eGFR <30 1 year prior to baseline and being on dialysis based on diagnosis Z992</p>
<p>Chronic heart failure NYHA IV</p>	<p>not applicable</p>

<p>End stage liver disease, defined as the presence of acute or chronic liver disease and recent history of one or more of the following: ascites, encephalopathy, variceal bleeding, bilirubin ≥ 2.0 mg/dL, albumin level ≤ 3.5 g/dL, prothrombin time ≥ 4 seconds prolonged, international normalised ratio (INR) ≥ 1.7 or prior liver transplant.</p>	<p>End stage liver disease (K729) looking 20 years back from baseline.</p>
<p>Female of child-bearing potential who is pregnant, breast-feeding or intends to become pregnant or is not using adequate contraceptive methods as required by local law or practice</p>	<p>Patients under 50 years of age are excluded.</p>
<p>Current or past (within the last 5 years) malignant neoplasms (except basal cell and squamous cell skin carcinoma)</p>	
<p>Other:</p> <p>Known or suspected hypersensitivity to trial products or related products</p> <p>Expected simultaneous participation in any other clinical trial of an investigational medicinal product. Participation in a clinical trial with stent(s) is allowed.</p> <p>Receipt of any investigational medicinal product within 30 days before randomisation. Brazil: Receipt of any investigational medicinal product within one year before randomisation unless there is a direct benefit to the subject at the investigator's discretion</p> <p>Any condition that in the investigator's opinion would make the subject unable to</p>	<p>All non-applicable</p>

adhere to the initial trial visit schedule and procedures	
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Time period

We will include patients between 2012-2022. For the current study, time zero is the first time the patient redeems a prescription of one of the pharmacotherapies of interest and fulfills the inclusion and exclusion criteria, during the time period of interest.

Discrete-time approximation of observed treatment

The aim of trial emulation is primarily to compare continuous treatment with Insulin degludec with continuous treatment with insulin glargine for 1-5 years. We will employ a discrete time scale with periods of six months and patients are considered on treatment in a time interval if at least one prescription was redeemed in that interval.

Target parameter

In this study, the main analysis for a comparison with DEVOTE is:

Take insulin degludec for 4 years versus take insulin glargine for 4 years.

For supplementary analyses, we are interested in the same contrast at 1,2,3, and 5 years.

Outcome(s)

Trial	Emulation
The primary composite cardiovascular outcome was defined as the first confirmed event of cardiovascular death, nonfatal myocardial infarction or nonfatal stroke.	CVD death, MI, stroke, as defined by ICD10-codes in Table 2; 10 and 4
The expanded composite cardiovascular outcome was the first confirmed event of the primary composite cardiovascular outcome with the addition of unstable angina pectoris leading to hospitalization	CVD death, MI, or stroke and UAP as defined by ICD10-codes in Table 2; 10, 4 and 12
Each component of the primary outcomes	Each individual outcome defined in table 2;

(CVD death, non fatal MI, nonfatal stroke)	10, 4 and 12
All cause death	All cause death
Non-cardiovascular death	Non-cvd death
Cardiovascular death excluding undetermined cause of death	Not pursued
Secondary hypoglycemic outcomes	Hospitalization due to severe hypoglycemia. Table 2: 13

*Definition of cardiovascular death: In the Danish setting, cardiovascular death can be defined by the Cause of Death registry in the whole study period except 2022. In 2022, we define cardiovascular death as any mortality occurrence where an I-diagnosis was present within 180 days before the death.

Adjustment variables

We include information on various confounders, pre-baseline, as well as time-varying, as specified in the following. Definitions are included in Tables 1-3 further below. Concomitant glucose-lowering treatment is included as a baseline covariate looking 180 days back from treatment initiation and included as time-varying confounders in case of initiation after baseline. Co-medication is defined as looking 180 days back from baseline, and history of comorbidities is defined as looking 10 years back from baseline.

The final choice of adjustment variables requires that support in analyses is ensured.

Baseline covariates

- Age (continuous)
- Sex
- Income (equivalized, 5-year mean)
- Degree of urbanization of home address (rural, suburban, or urban) (DEGURBA)
- Education, ISCED class
- Duration of Diabetes, categorized as 0-5, 5-10, >10 years
- HbA1c (continuous), latest maximum 1 year before baseline
- History of Ischemic heart disease
- History of Heart Failure
- History of Stroke

- History of Peripheral artery disease
- History of Renal disease
- History of Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease
- History of Hypertension
- History of Atrial Fibrillation
- Therapy with aldosterone receptor antagonists, beta-blockers, angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors/angiotensin receptor-2 blockers, loop diuretics, calcium channel blockers, thiazide, acetylsalicylic acid, statins
- Glucose-lowering therapy use beyond those included in the treatment regimes.

Comedication is defined by ATC-codes in Table 1 and comorbidities are defined by ICD-10 and ATC-codes in Table 2.

Time-dependent variables

- Adding GLP-1
- Adding SGLT2i
- Adding other glucose lowering treatments
- Incident Ischemic heart disease
- Incident heart failure
- Incident Peripheral artery disease
- Incident renal disease
- Incident chronic obstructive pulmonary disease
- Incident hypertension
- Incident Atrial Fibrillation

Descriptive analyses

A series of descriptive analyses will be made. These will include the following questions using non-parametric analyses:

1. Baseline characteristics of the two study arms
2. Calendar year of inclusion for each study arm
3. Time to administrative censoring or loss to follow-up
4. Time to treatment discontinuation, by treatment, accounting for death, emigration, and administrative censoring
5. Time to any additional add-on
6. Number of primary and secondary outcomes by initial treatment

Statistical estimation

We will employ a discrete time scale with periods of six months. We estimate the target parameters with a longitudinal targeted minimum loss estimator (Petersen 2014, Lendle 2017). The estimator updates an initial sequential regression estimator using inverse probability weighting (propensity of treatment, probability of not being censored). All nuisance parameter regression models needed for the initial estimator and for the targeting step are adjusted for additive effects of all covariates, updated to the current time interval, such that we never confuse the causal time order of the variables. Specifically, we regress the outcome/treatment/censoring variables defined in the calendar time interval $(t, t+6 \text{ months}]$ on the most recent values of the time-dependent covariates at time t and the whole history of the treatment variables at time t . All nuisance parameter models were fitted using penalized ridge regression selecting the penalty parameters such as to undersmooth the regression fits. For continuous variables, we employ flexible modeling techniques, including linear modeling, spline-based adjustments, and categorization of continuous variables, using diverse super learners. We do not truncate propensity scores and censoring probabilities. Reported are the longitudinal targeted minimum loss estimates (LTMLE) with 95% confidence intervals.

Subgroups:

We will repeat the analysis of the primary and secondary outcomes in the same subgroups as they did in the devote trial where possible.

Sensitivity analyses:

For sensitivity analysis, we will employ a grace period of 30 days, moving the index date to day 30 after treatment initiation and repeating the main analysis.

Analysis of a non-trial broad population:

In addition to the analysis above we will pursue the same analysis in a broad non-trial population with the aim of investigating the same endpoints (continuous usage of glargine compared to degludec). The population in question is as follows:

Inclusion and exclusion criteria
Individuals over or equal to 40 years of age and less than 90 years of age will be included
Insulin Degludec or Glargine must be taken on top of metformin
There must be an Hba1c level present at baseline (1 year prior to index) and it must be over 48 mmol/mol
The presence of any CVD criteria as mentioned in the trial emulation results in exclusion. Diagnosis codes present in table 2. (1,3,4,5,10,11,12)
A eGFR of less than 30 ml/min measured within 2 years from baseline results in exclusion
Patients who immigrated into the country less than 10 years prior to baseline are excluded.

The main outcome will be investigated in subgroups of sociodemographic factors such as sex, age, income, and education, as well as disease markers such as diabetes duration and HbA1c.

Table 1: Definitions of medication types

Drug	ATC code
Mineralocorticoids	C03D
Beta-blocker	C07
Renin-angiotensin system inhibitor	C09
Loop diuretics	C03C, C03EB
Calcium channel blockers	C08
Thiazide	CO3A
Acetylsalicylic acid	B01AC06, NO2BA01
Statin	C10A, A10BH51, A10BH52

Table 2: Definitions of diseases

	Disease	ICD-10	ATC code
1	Heart failure	I110, I130, I132, I420, I426-I429, I50	
2	Hypertension*	I10, I109, I11, I110, I119, I119A, I12, I120, I129, I13, I130, I131, I132, I139, I15, I150, I151, I152, I158, I159	CO2A, CO2B, CO2C, CO2DA, CO2DB, CO2DD, CO2DG, CO2L, CO3A, CO3B, CO3D, CO3E, CO3X, CO7A, CO7B, CO7C, CO7D, CO7F, CO8, CO9AA, CO9BA, CO9BB, CO9CA, CO9DA, CO9DB, CO9XA02, CO9XA52
3	Ischemic heart disease	I20, I23, I24, I25	
4	Stroke	I60-61, I63-64, G45	
5	Peripheral vascular disease	I70, I739	
6	Chronic renal disease	N03-N05, N07-08, N11, N18-19, N26, N162-164, N168, N250, Q612-13, Q615, Q619 E112, E142 I120, I131-32	
7	Atrial fibrillation	I48	
8	Cancer, except non-melanoma skin cancer	C00-C97	
9	Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	J42, J44	
10	Myocardial infarction	I21	
11	Revascularization	O20, O21, O27, O34, O37, O4	
12	Unstable angina	I20	
13	Hypoglycemia	E159, E160, E161, E162	

*Hypertension when defined by ATC requires at least two distinct redemption of prescriptions in two consecutive quarters. Date of hypertension, defined by the last of these redemptions.

Table 3: ATC codes to define glucose-lowering drug classes

Drug class	ATC-codes
Insulin (all)	A10A
Insulin Degludec	A10AE06 (Tresiba) A10AD06 (Ryzodeg)
Insulin Glargin	A10AE04 (Lantus, Toujeo, Senglee, Abasaglar KwikPen)
Biguanide	A10BA01, A10BA03, A10BD01
Metformin	A10BA02, A10BD02-3, A10BD05, A10BD07-8, A10B10-11, A10BD20, A10BD22-23, A10BD25-27
Sulfonylurea	A10BB, A10BDO1, A10BD04, A10BDO
Alfa glucosidase inhib	A10BF, A10BD17
Thiazolidinedione (Glitazones)	A10BG, A10BD03-06, A10BD09, A10BD12, A10BD26
DPP4 inhibitors	A10BH, A10BD07-13, A10BD18, A10BD19, A10BD21, A10BD22, A10BD24-25, A20BD27
SGLT2 inhibitors	A10BK, A10BD15-16, A10BD19-21, A10BD23-25, A10BD27
GLP1-RA	A10BJ, A10AE54, A10AE56